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CURRENT STATE AND PERSPECTIVES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL TOURISM IN UKRAINE

Kostynets Valeriia. Current state and perspectives for the development of industrial tourism in Ukraine.

The article discusses the issue of current trends and the further development of industrial tourism in Ukraine. This analysis is conducted through the prism of world experience in the development of industrial tourism. The tourism cluster of Kryvyi Rih as a centre for the development of industrial tourism is separately identified. It is separately established that there are a large number of barriers, which are due to the specific activity of industrial enterprises and non-core tourist activities for them, as well as the existence of additional conditions for ensuring the safety of both visitors and tourism. The author emphasizes that one of the main recommendations is the choice of a strategy of concentration in production enterprises that are purely industrial. The author has determined that when planning a strategy for the development of industrial tourism, it is necessary to focus on historically significant objects, which represent a unique heritage and can become a winning product portfolio of industrial tourism.

Key words: industrial tourism, tourism sector, non-traditional tourism product, tourism, tourist services.

Костинець В.В. Сучасний стан і перспективи розвитку промислового туризму в Україні. У статті висвітлюється проблема сучасних тенденцій і подальшого розвитку промислового туризму в Україні. Цей аналіз проводиться через призму світового досвіду розвитку промислового туризму. Встановлено, що серйозний досвід в області розвитку промислового туризму накопичено в країнах Заходу, які відносяться до числа найбільш зрілих ринків туристського продукту. Виокремлений туристичний кластер Кривого Рогу як центру розвитку промислового туризму. Окремо встановлено, що існує велика кількість бар'єрів, які обумовлені специфічною діяльністю промислових підприємств і непрофільною туристичною діяльністю для них, а також наявністю додаткових умов для забезпечення безпеки як відвідувачів, так і сфери туризму. Автор підкреслює, що однією з основних рекомендацій є вибір стратегії концентрації на виробничих підприємствах, які є суто промисловими. В статті визначено, що промислові підприємства орієнтуються на кілька цільових груп потенційних споживачів, але існує обмежена кількість каналів комунікації та залучення споживачів: через анонсування на інтернет-порталах з анонсами заходів, через наявність власних груп в соціальних мережах, через туристичні компанії. Окремо автор зазначає, що існує досить жорстка вимога до продукту – екскурсії, частина або вся екскурсія повинні бути спрямовані на демонстрацію або розповідь про виробничий процес підприємства. В свою чергу, для індивідуальних споживачів найбільш цікавими і привабливими є екскурсії, які вони можуть відвідати самостійно, не у складі групи. Автор наголошує на тому, що однією з основних рекомендацій є вибір стратегії концентрації на виробничих підприємствах, які є чисто виробничими. Ці підприємства мають потребу в допомозі та підтримці з боку регіональних органів влади, профільних міністерств і відомств в організації туристичної діяльності. Автором визначено, що при плануванні стратегії розвитку промислового туризму необхідно концентруватися на історично значущих об'єктах, які протягом довгого часу існують в конкретному регіоні, і майданчиках з цікавою технологією виробництва, які являють собою унікальну спадщину та можуть стати виграшним продуктивним портфелем промислового туризму.

Ключові слова: промисловий туризм, туристичний сектор, нетрадиційний туристичний продукт, туризм, туристичні послуги.

Костинець В.В. Современное состояние и перспективы развития промышленного туризма в Украине.

В статье обсуждается проблема современных тенденций и дальнейшего развития промышленного туризма в Украине. Этот анализ проводится через призму мирового опыта в развитии промышленного туризма. Туристический кластер Кривого Рога как центр развития индустриального туризма выделен отдельно. Отдельно установлено, что существует большое количество барьеров, которые обусловлены специфической деятельностью промышленных предприятий и непрофильной туристической деятельностью для них, а также нали-

чем дополнительных условий для обеспечения безопасности как посетителей, так и сферы туризма. Автор подчеркивает, что одной из основных рекомендаций является выбор стратегии концентрации на производственных предприятиях, которые являются сугубо промышленными. Определено, что при планировании стратегии развития промышленного туризма необходимо концентрироваться на исторически значимых объектах, которые представляют собой уникальное наследие и могут стать выигрышным продуктовым портфелем промышленного туризма.

Ключевые слова: промышленный туризм, туристический сектор, нетрадиционный туристический продукт, туризм, туристические услуги.

Problem statement. The modern tourism industry offers sophisticated new so-called special types of travel for the client. Tourists of the 21st century strive not only to learn something interesting or get well during the tour but also get different experiences with visiting new, previously “closed” places. Today there is a new “Era of impressions and sensations” when more and more popular various extreme and non-traditional types of tourism are becoming. In this vein, industrial tourism has real prospects for the development of domestic and inbound tourism.

Industrial tourism is connected with the organization of excursions and regular tours to the leading existing or previously functioning industrial enterprises of the country. Not only ordinary tourists but also schoolchildren, students, businessmen and business leaders, journalists, each of whom will pursue its purpose when visiting the production, may be among the main consumers of industrial tourism objects. The given direction of tourism, taking into account the existing production base in the territory of any region, can function effectively, and at the expense of its specificity – give impetus to the development of small and medium-sized enterprises, which will also serve as a factor of development of a certain region and can become its competitive advantage.

Analysis of recent researches and publications and separation of previously unresolved parts of the main problem. The theme of the development of industrial tourism in the world as a whole and Ukraine in particular was raised in the scientific works of such scientists as F. Bran [7], P. Bujok [8], E.A. Frew [9], J. Jelinek [8], R. Kadyrov [3], M. Klempa [8], A. Medyanik [4], Yu. Nikulina [5], M. Porzer [8], Zh. Yermakova [2], and others. In turn, research from domestic economists on the development of this type of segment of the tourism business in the national periodicals we almost don't meet. An exception is the research of V. Sorochan [6]. It is worth noting that industrial tourism is a relatively new phenomenon and interdisciplinary, in connection with which it is poorly developed from a scientific point of view. Based on this, the question of studying the features of the development of industrial tourism in Ukraine is quite relevant.

The aim of the article. The purpose of the research – to analyse current trends and determine the prospects for the development of industrial tourism in Ukraine.

Presentation of the main research material. The development of industrial tourism is an effective mechanism in creating and promoting a positive image of the territory and an effective marketing tool for attracting investors and tourists. In addition, industrial tourism projects give impetus to other sectors of the economy, both in the region and in the country as a whole, related to the tourist flow service. These include: food, accommodation, transportation and more. The introduction of industrial tourism at the

regional level has a positive impact on the regional budget due to tax revenues in connection with increased turnover, development of small and medium-sized businesses, investment attractiveness, direct and indirect employment, and other factors. Advantages from the organization and development of industrial tourism at the micro level are to increase the volume of products produced, improve the quality of goods, create a positive image of the company, promote the brand of the company, attract investors, search for young professionals.

Although industrial tourism does not occupy a dominant position in the global tourism services market, it has clearly occupied a niche abroad. Today, the world is represented by a large number of examples of cities that successfully invite tourists to their businesses. In France alone, by 2018, 1700 companies have invited tourists to their production sites. The leader in the level of promotion of such industrial excursions is the tidal power plant in Rance, which receives 300,000 tourists annually. In England, the Cedarberry Chocolate Factory is visited by 400,000 people each year. However, pioneers in industrial tourism are considered American companies. The first-ever industrial excursion was a visit by tourists to Jack Daniel's production in 1866. Today, businesses that do not take tourists on excursions in the United States are very few. For any serious company – be it a car assembly plant, a sawmill or an airport – it is considered bad to not invite tourists, it is a threat to the company's reputation [10, p. 398]. Mining tourism is widespread in Poland (Wieliczka and Bochnia mines), Sweden (Kiruna iron ore mines), Estonia (Kohtla-Nimme shale mines), Norway (Roros copper mine), Czech Republic (Kutna Hora silver mine), Slovakia (Banská Štiavnica), Chile (Chukikamata copper mine), South Africa (Kimberley diamond mines), Australia (Tennant Creek gold mines), Finland [9, p. 30].

Particular attention is paid to the development of ecological routes, the inclusion of the natural world in the value orientations of the individual, which will contribute to the introduction of ethical norms of communication and attitude to nature in public life. We are talking about the peculiarities of the functioning of industrial attractions within the industrial cities, which today are able to meet the educational and recreational needs of the population. There is worldwide experience in learning about the peculiarities of the country's industrial heritage, particularly in Germany. It is a well-known “Production Heritage Route”, which has been introduced in the Ruhr District since 1999 and has been operating successfully for two decades, during which tourists can visit 19 settlements presenting the regional history of coal and steel production. Ukraine has great potential for both anthropogenic landscapes, as well as a large number of man-made landscapes, technological artifacts,

industrial landscapes that can be effectively used as objects of industrial tourism.

An analysis of the world experience and practice of organizing and conducting industrial excursions suggests that industrial tourism is a destination in tourism, which provides industrial space as an object of tourist display. Considering that tourism today has become a social phenomenon and has moved from an elite product category to a product category accessible to the consumer, it is important to attract consumers' attention to non-standard tourist products, including industrial tours.

Accordingly, in the development of industrial tours and excursions, it is necessary to distinguish production facilities in two directions: objects of historical and industrial heritage, which are not only monuments of industrial tourism but also cognitive ones; modern operating enterprises, which, in addition to industrial excursions, it is expedient to use as educational or business tours [8, p. 87].

Tours and excursions of objects of historical and industrial heritage should be called industrial tour – a component of industrial tourism. This interpretation is due to the fact that the purpose and objectives of such tours are to familiarize themselves with the production capabilities and features of the development of past industrial eras. In addition, tours of historical and industrial sites reveal the issues of ethnography, production technology, production facilities, and other features of past centuries.

It is advisable to call tours of modern operating enterprises industrial. They are aimed at the acquaintance with modern technological and technological achievements and scientific potential, quality of the manufactured products, production process. Industrial tours, depending on the specialization of the enterprise, can be divided into industries. Also, the importance of the organization of industrial excursions should pay attention to the age category of excursionists. For example, the purpose of such tours for students is professional orientation, the satisfaction of cognitive needs, for students – acquaintance with the scientific and technical potential and technological process, for people of mature generation is interesting the process of production and quality of products.

It should be noted that in the regions of Ukraine, industrial tourism is of a point of nature and not of widespread use. The most promising centre for the development of industrial tourism in Ukraine today is Kryvyi Rih. Kryvyi Rih is characterized by a rich industrial heritage, which includes the remains of production facilities, railways, hydraulic structures, bridges, ancient mining landscapes, remnants of working settlements, etc. If the area of the city of Kryvyi Rih is 431 km², mining landscapes in it occupy about 48.8% of the territory and it is constantly growing [1]. Such industrial heritage requires optimal use of the tourist-recreational load to conserve tourist resources, to obtain socio-economic effect without disturbing the ecological balance of the environment. It is about working industrial sites and the remnants of industrial heritage. The presence of such a non-standard tourist product of Kryvorizhzhya as industrial tourism allows creating creative excursion programs with unique objects: underground, transport, museums of the history of industrial enterprise, socio-cultural attractions related to the industrial past of the region. For example, in the city there are industrial excursions “Northern Lights of Kryvyi Rih”, “Kryvyi Rih – Miner”, “Descent into the Operating Mine”, etc.; review “Night Kryvyi Rih

from the Height of the Petrovsky Dump”, “Kryvyi Rih – the City of Ore and Metal”; the event “Festival of Industrial Culture Night”; Historic Streets of the Old Town, Old Gdantsevsky Mine, To the Old Red Layer Mine, and others.

As practice shows, tourist activity in large industrial centres suffers from a great deal of formalization, and therefore, is oriented towards the production of relevant services as a commodity of mass culture. As tourists increase their needs for quality services, it is necessary to take into account environmental components and introduce the instrumental values of industrial tourism as a socio-cultural practice. The traditional industrial city – Kryvyi Rih – is no exception and was considered an area of increased risk to human life and health. Thus, according to the theory of reflexive modernization, every person, regardless of their status and age, lives in a society of risk. At the same time, it is the extremity of the industrial zones that drives people to travel to such places.

Industrial tourism can greatly enhance the image of the modern industrial region and city. The positive image of the industrial region will be formed more successfully under the conditions of: availability of excursions and other tourist services; meeting cognitive needs; cultural and educational actions; acquaintance with the extraordinary, amazing results of the impact of industrial production technology on the geospatial landscape composition [4, p. 31]. It is industrial tourism that is able to meet the demand for excursions for certain social groups of the population, to influence the rational-careful attitude and use of natural resources. In particular, the experience of Kryvorizhzhya on planting trees and plants on waste heaps by residents of the city with the involvement of student youth is interesting. The acquired social and environmental experience can be used during the organization and conducting of excursions of environmental topics. Introduced environmental excursion routes within the industrial city demonstrate the effects of resource misuse and open up opportunities for the restoration of post-industrial landscapes. The development and implementation of instrumental values of eco-tourism activities will allow modern youth to determine the range of quality tourism services that will create the best conditions for the formation of ecological culture as the quality of personality.

Kryvyi Rih has an extensive multifaceted structure of industrial objects, various specialized industrial enterprises. The industrial heritage of Kryvyi Rih is a system of unique mining and industrial landscapes of European importance, unique engineering and technogenic formations. The tourist attractiveness of the region requires creative offers to the consumer of tourist services with unique objects of industrial destinations, organization of tours with industrial objects, creation of unique industrial museums based on quality advertising and information materials. At the same time, achieving an optimal tourist and recreational load for the conservation of tourist resources should be an important task.

It should be noted that there are restrictions that hinder the development of industrial tourism in general, including in the regions of Ukraine. First of all, it is worth noting the issues related to the security of the visitors themselves. Businesses have to develop business visit regulations that include visitor safety briefing. In addition, this barrier limits the number of visitors to 25 people per trip, which is a limitation of the capacity of industrial excursions.

Another barrier is the safety of the product itself, which is related to the specifics of the production process and the preservation of those modes that are necessary to ensure the quality of the manufactured products.

Information security is also a barrier to the organization of production excursions. It has risks associated with the release of a new leakage product that will result in loss and loss of profit. To prevent these risks, companies limit their ability to visit their production facilities during periods of work on a new product.

In addition to the security of information, a significant obstacle is its limited organization of excursions to industrial enterprises. At present, there is no single information and consulting centre in Ukraine that would provide complete information on manufacturing enterprises that are ready to host tourist groups on their territory. Developing this or that route in the business entity, it is necessary to clearly regulate the time of visit, to develop a master class for the participation of tourists in the production of specific products, to develop game modules (competitive competitions), to prepare a guide, to provide tourists with souvenirs made on this enterprise. The financial costs of organizing an excursion route at existing enterprises are usually insignificant since there is no need to create a logistical base for receiving tourists and demonstrating the production process.

A certain problem is also the lack of openness to the tourism of a number of industrial enterprises. Quite often large industrial entities with interesting hardware and technological processes and innovative processes are left out of the possibility of increasing their own tourist attraction. In domestic practice, unlike foreign experience, enterprises do not practice openness and hospitality for outsiders. To some extent, this is due to the fact that some business entities are required to provide safety training or a throughput system. However, it is worth noting that the principle of openness of the production process for tour groups can improve the reputation of the company. As a rule, such business entities have a more presentable appearance,

demonstrating to their visitors the cleanliness of the workplace, the use of modern technological equipment.

Finally, another obstacle to organizing excursions for industrial enterprises is the complexity of controlling tourists themselves. This definition implies the control of tourists before the visit. There is no strict agreement on the excursion to specific groups, therefore, often there are situations when a group of tourists at the last moment refuses to visit the excursion. However, it does not incur any losses but the enterprise itself can no longer undertake a production tour, resulting in downtime, which could be visited by more interested potential visitors [2, p. 170].

Conclusions. On this basis, one of the main recommendations is the choice of a concentration strategy for manufacturing enterprises that are purely industrial. These businesses need assistance and support from regional authorities, line ministries and agencies in organizing tourism activities. It is necessary to regulate which undertakings may relate to industrial tourism and what characteristics they must possess in order to be classified as industrial tourism.

Talking about concentration in a particular segment, within the strategy for the promotion of industrial tourism, it is necessary to concentrate on historically significant objects that have existed in a particular region for a long time, and sites with interesting production technology (metro, nuclear power plant, automotive plant, plastic factory toys, etc.). These sites represent a unique heritage that can become a winning industrial tourism product portfolio. In general, the prospects for the development of industrial tourism in some regions of Ukraine are related not only to the availability of suitable facilities for this purpose but also to the expected increase in population demand for non-traditional types of tourist services in terms of orientation towards domestic tourism, as well as to the fact that stabilization the situation in the domestic market for tourist services is possible only through the diversification of the latter, including through the development of industrial tourism.

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